

HPC SERVICES

Free support, guidance & advice in optimising & porting source code to modern HPC systems

Some examples of our services...

PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT

ESMValTool: Earth System Evaluation Tool

Performance improvement and parallelization using Dask

PROFILING & COMPUTATIONAL OPTIMIZATION

GLOBO: Atmospheric General Circulation Model

Profiling, optimizing MPI communications, Parallel I/O and Mixed/lower precision

GPU PORTING & OPTIMIZATION

CAMP: Chemistry Across Multiple Phases

Revising and optimizing GPU implementation of CAMP for new HPC systems, focusing on MareNostrum5

REDUCED PRECISION FOR ESM

EC-EARTH 4: European Community Earth System Model

Porting M7 aerosols in OpenIFS 48r1 to single precision to gain performance without degrading quality

... and much more!

More info:

www.esiwace.eu/services

